

Braintasking: a new one-shot goal achievement mode for automatic higher performance by productive partial mind dissociation with critical ability preserved

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This work discloses some results of a novel general ultrarapid behaviour change mechanism providing self-controllable one-shot automatic higher performance ability via a simple partial-dissociative commandable-brain construct - personification of the *brain* as the goal-tasking agent, *not* the mind. Partial temporary dissociation of the mind to obtain one-shot higher performances gains of cognition, behaviour and affect was successfully achieved for simple and complex goal tasks with full retention of critical mental ability and observer status for case rapid (i) attitude change, (ii) mood-regulation, (iii) physical mobility improvements in arthritis, (iv) tinnitus distress reduction, (v) recovery during cardiac failure, (vi) intentional-forgetting and (vii) boosted motivation during fatigue - clearly indicating an effective high performance control interface is establishable with a reasonable task-consciousness control-type tradeoff.

Notably, several valuable *unconditioned* new capabilities were also found by the method, including: (1) one-shot ability to instantly effect complete suspension of all active cardiac failure symptoms and arousal dysregulation (loss of gait and balance control, irregular heartbeat, confusion, low affect, blurred vision, weakness, impaired respiration) within 1000msec post single brief command only (2 occasions); (2) sudden (unexpected) in-brain development and application of a neural network semantic category-selective sound filter fully within 1000msec effective in moderating severe pulsatile tinnitus distress for 14 days; (3) an unique 'encryption' algorithm seemingly innately possessed by the brain invocable to aid desired one-shot intentional forgetting.

These latter latent capability accesses support that the mode of addressing the personified brain as the tasked agent obliged to perform provides actual access control to formerly-unknown and superior low-level *brain-owned and managed* performance abilities bearing some genuine gains of adaptive function on demand.

We distinguish between the initial partial mental *distancing* here required for triggering a desired one-shot behaviour - via a preliminary momentary thought-stopping, followed by an *insistent* single goal performance demand 'to the personified brain' to perform it - and the subsequent temporary partial automatic *dissociation* (and 'freeing') of the mind from the *active selection or control* of goal task *performance enactive steps* and/or effort control as the demanded goal achievement is being successfully performed.

We term the effective stimulus type which enables this one-shot braintasking mode an **onstruction** - a single brief goal performance demand instruction (goal command only, see examples below) directed 'to the brain' enabling high-performance ability automatically on first go with or without subsequent ongoing partial dissociation of the mind from the performance, providing high-ability onset in approximately 1 second. Up to 7 onstructions were found performable concurrently with ease. Equally, we term the agentic faculty of the brain providing one-shot higher performance behaviour within productive dissociation the human ontelagence.

Keywords:

dissociation, arthritis mobility, tinnitus distress, pulsatile tinnitus, attitude change, self-regulation of affect, motivation, one-shot achievement, gain of function.

1. Mental-only performance goals (eg. attitude change, mood regulation) may be achieved in 1 second.

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Some Case Example Onstructions and Found Effects: Brief Summary

Attitude

1. 'Brain...damp (reduce) negativity!'

Effect: 4.5 successive days of rapid discounting of each negative thought upon its occurrence by automatic logical *double negation*.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

Affect (morale)

2. 'Brain! Delete moping! (sadness)'

Effect: 57+ successive days of extinction of chronic sad affect (by stimulated automatic absence) with autorecovery of practical focus.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

Tinnitus Distress and Symptom Reduction

3. 'Brain! Stop that ***** sound!'

Effect: 14 days of automatic sound modulation by partial phonemic alteration of each word of a distressing high frequency-of-occurrence 3 word category perceived in phoneme-associative type pulsatile tinnitus.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

4. 'Brain! Delete tinnitus (false) word-associations!'

Effect: 735+ successive days extinction of distressing associations of pulsatile tinnitus sound frequencies autoforming perceived 'words' versus hundreds prior per day > 5 mo. Effect ongoing.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

5. 'Brain...Stop tinnitus annoyance!'

Effect: 37 successive days of significantly reduced distress (annoyance) at having tinnitus.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

Mobility Improvements: OA Chronic Knee Pain²

6. 'Brain...straighten me up'

Effect: Smooth automatic correction of gait and posture from a stooped standing position with weight balance autocorrected on each foot, feet automoved equidistant from hips. 5+ occasions. Transient dissociation of motor control during.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

7. 'Brain, get me up! (out of chair)'

Effect: Smooth prompt stand up movement from sitting position without usual pain or need to use arm-rests for assist. 7x in rapid succession (< 2 min). Transient dissociation of motor control while rising motion performed only.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

8. 'Brain...get me home!' 500m rtn walk trial

Effect: Sudden correction and regularisation of walking gait with posture autoadjusted to a more upright position, pace improvement. Pain rating reduction from 5/7 prior to 1/7 during. Efficacious transient dissociation of motor control - i.e. transfer to ontelagent motor control - over the full distance.

"My body just went into a smooth rhythmic 'automatic walk'... I was free to look around and didn't have to focus on my steps or knees at all, which surprised me. I haven't walked that well in 5 years! I had no pain walking the last 70m (up the hill)." - S.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

9. 'Brain...get me up (the stairs)'

Effect: Steady ascent of stairs without pause, need to use the handrail and without pain through the transit. > 15 occasions. Transient dissociation of motor control while ascending only.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

2 S: a senior M on clinic bilateral knee-replacement readiness watchlist.

Cardiac Event Recovery³

10. 'Brain...get me home (alive)'

Effect: Instant suspension of all active cardiac and arousal dysregulation symptoms (loss of gait and balance control, irregular heartbeat, confusion, low affect, blurred vision, weakness, impaired respiration) within 1000msec post single brief command only. Productive transfer to ontelagent control [Occasion 1 - Sept. 2021]:

"It was dark, after 8.30pm and I'd spent all day sitting alone in a chair with my heart symptoms: arrhythmias, breathing problems, confusion, chest pain, eyes blurring on and off, near blackouts. I decided to walk to the store for tobacco, for comfort.

I got 270m along the 1.6km journey, and I almost blacked out and hit the road falling backwards. All symptoms hit in one go - and my left leg went left, my right leg to the right (not straight), I'd lost leg control while crossing the road.

I fought to stay standing and conscious for about 15 seconds desperately. It passed enough for me to swear at myself and get across.

I had 4 more episodes the same before I reached the store. I walked in in a state of near delirium, barely holding it together. I badly needed a doctor but I'd left my phone at home.

I got the baccy, lit up, and tried to get home.

I made 300m on the journey back when I had my next attack. I told myself, 'i've done harder things than walking, been through more pain than this'. It cheered me up - for 11 steps I had more control.

*I got about 450m from home when I had the 8th attack of the journey. And as I stood swaying on the spot, I realised I'd nuthin left in the tank. I 'knew' I wasn't going to make it, as I was about (to) fall forward and hit the ground face-first, I was blacking-out, heart *****.*

As I swayed in those last few seconds - to my surprise - I heard my mind quietly say 'brain... ..get me home' (alive) just as I was falling forward and losing consciousness.

Then a near 'miracle' happened. So fast, it took me about 5 seconds to realise what was going on.

*I didn't fall! I hadn't hit the ground....I was already about 4 meters further along the road, and I was being marched home by my body automatically. At high speed. Faster than I ever remember marching as an Army cadet. In ****perfect health****. All symptoms gone. They just vanished when I gave the 'command' to my brain. Confusion, chest pain, heart arrhythmia, loss of leg strength and control, blurred eyesight...- everything - all symptoms just gone.*

When I realised that I cheerily started to whistle! I felt great...though I wasn't sure how long it would last. I watched what my body was doing - it was marching me home at high speed and I didn't have to do anything - look out for obstacles on the uneven dark path? - nope. Monitor my pace? Nope. Manage my breathing? Worry about my heart? My strength? Nope, nothing. Not necessary.

When I got home I sat down amazed at what just happened, puffing, (then) made notes fast.

I realised I'd just experienced a 'get me to the chopper' ability I never knew I had before. I firmly believe I am only alive to this day because of that. Thank God...I got to see my children again.

P.S. My symptoms then stayed gone for the rest of the night." - S.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

11. 'Brain! ***** fix it your **SELF!**'

Effect: as at 10. Duration 19 minutes only [Occasion 2 - Dec. 8 2021].

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

3 S: Middle-aged M diagnosed with Tachycardia Arrhythmia 11mo prior.

Notes

1. Further independent investigation is recommended to investigate the efficacy of alternately affirmative positive language.

2. Wider investigation is required to determine the generality and programmable task-scope of the mode, in particular with gain-focussed and maintenance goals in addition to recovery goal achievement.

3. Mode effect durations follow the expected pattern from shortest to longest via the keywords 'reduce', 'stop', 'delete' respectively.

4. An aspect of ontelagent **decision-making** can be probed using generically worded literal onstruction phrases, such as 'brain! Activity!' and 'brain! Decide!' with or without a target intent. For example, a generic 'Activity!' onstruction with the intent 'get up, Im exhausted, go in and rest' resulted in one case in naggingly too-long garden grass being cut effortlessly ontelagently for 25 minutes instead despite "complete beforehand lack of motivation or intent" to do so in the context of end-of-workday fatigue.

5. Comfortable exit of any mode-associated metacognitive state may be achieved by a resortive onstruction of the intent. For example:

'Brain! Usual thinking only' |
'braintasking...Off!' |
'Exit onstruction mode!' |
'Brain! Be practical!'

Successful exit of braintasking mode and any introspective state should be immediately obvious: is the next thought automatic interest in a more ordinary matter?

6. A case onstruction targetting anxiety in a Cautious Regulatory Fit adult male terminated the condition with immediate effect on first go (one-shot) with no subsequent effort required

to maintain the improved state. This effect was also successfully experimentally reversed on day 4 using the inverse onstruction to test programmability. The onstruction:

'Brain! No secondaries !'

(Intent: prevent 'second-thoughts' / follow-on negative thoughts occurring after a first one)

Effect: An alternate mental state of calm with sustained moderate optimism and "happiness" (-S) without effort by automatic full absence of negative thought-runs (extinction of rumination ability) for 72 hours was produced. No negative effects on motivation, behaviour or cognition.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

Similarly, in a case of white collar professional occupational anxiety, the onstruction:

'Brain...delete *irrelevant* doubts about my work!'

Effect: 40+ successive days extinction of irrelevant work doubts by their automatic absence with no self-monitoring required. Anxiety replaced by a calm realistic optimism and increased satisfaction with work role.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

Analgesia

7. The S with osteoarthritis chronic knee pain (see p.2) recently obtained the following onstruction results:

'Brain! No knee pain!'

Effect (1st use) 56 successive days extinction of chronic knee pain (by its full automatic absence) 24/7 for both knees simultaneously. Dec 20 2022 - Feb 16 2023.

Onset: instant. One-shot. Effortless (automatic).

Effect (2nd use) 16 days, as above Feb 16 – Mar 4 2023.

Effect (3rd use) 470+ days, as above. Effect ongoing.

8. Notably, a second use of onstruction #5 on page 2 by the *S* had the further effect of eliminating personal annoyance at having tinnitus for over 270 days. The *S* has since repeated the onstruction for a 3rd time and the positive effect (absence of tinnitus distress) is ongoing.